

SOCIAL SCIENCES

THE INFLUENCE OF THE PRESS: DIARIO LA MAÑANA IN CORRIENTES, ARGENTINA IN THE MIDDLE OF THE 20TH CENTURY

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Abstract

In this article we investigate by reading the newspaper La Mañana from March 13 to December 22, 1949, how the economy of the province of Corrientes Argentina is reflected in its publications, with Filomeno Velazco being governor and we intend to identify its influence on society. It is a relevant topic for the construction of our recent history since it allows us to know the conditions of existence and development of the people of Corrientes in their economic activities. The first findings we obtained have to do with the temporal delimitation that coincided with the development and rise of the Justicialist government of Juan Domingo Perón. In conclusion, the press in Corrientes contributes to the dissemination of information for citizens, with which we can say that it is a space that generates ideas, as well as a forum for the permanent defense of freedom. The sources consulted in the General Archive of the Province constitute the basis of the investigation.

Keywords: Economy, society, newspaper, media, state.

Introduction.

“The history of Argentine journalism is multifaceted and rich. From the beginning of our life as a free country, the written press was a vehicle to project ideas, promote progress initiatives, collect civic concerns, disseminate political platforms and social desires, expose various scientific, literary and artistic expressions. Fertile ground for constructive and peaceful debate, it was also, on multiple occasions, a field of harsh and relentless confrontations” (De Marco, Miguel Ángel. 2006-9).

Through the newspaper, La Mañana we carried out the investigation during the government of General Filomeno Velazco from March 13 to December 22, 1949; It is a contribution to understanding some economic aspects of the provincial past that have been little studied and analyzed until now. With this work we propose to clarify if during the first year of Filomeno Velazco's government the Corrientes press reflects the reality of the economic situation, we seek to know what was published in economic matters during this stage in the provincial territory. The Economy in the province of Corrientes is a relevant topic for the construction of our recent history since it allows us to know the conditions of existence and development of the people of Corrientes in their economic activities.

The sources consulted in the General Archive of the Province constitute the basis of the research, allowing it to be viable to carry out the work. In addition, general and specific biography will also be used to provide theoretical support for this production.

The present investigation is based on and has as its main source the publications of the year 1949, of the newspaper LA Mañana, which began its activities on February 2, 1930. The address and administration of said newspaper is on Buenos Aires Street at 408 the city of Corrientes; It is distributed throughout the country with representatives in Buenos Aires, Jorge Oscar Linari, (Florida 229-8 Piso u.). On March 24, 1949, the format change of the newspaper occurred "after 19 years of existence in the country's newspapers with the

manual format and synthetic style, we are forced to change it. From this issue we took the large format. We seek to defend ourselves since Times are hard and to obtain entry into the advertising media of the federal capital... this newspaper with the largest circulation in the province reaches even the most remote corner." (Diario La Mañana. 1949, May 24, p3.).

Investigation.

We will briefly comment on the biographical data of General Juan Filomeno Velzco, he was born on July 5, 1892 in the city of Esquina, province of Corrientes, son of Eustaquio Velazco and Marcelina Martínez. He entered the Nation's military college in 1909 and in 1913 he graduated as a sub. Lieutenant. In 1930, while he was stationed in Concepción del Uruguay, the revolution of September 6 of Corrientes occurred and the de facto president José Félix Uriburu appointed him to serve as Secretary of the Interior of the Presidency of the Republic. Later he served in the Headquarters of the Security Guard of the Buenos Aires City Police and then Chief of the Arsenal Battalion. Being Chief of the 15th regiment of the city of La Rioja, the revolution of June 4, 1943 took place and the Government that emerged from it appointed him Interim Federal Comptroller until the appointment of the head. The President of the Republic, General Edelmiro J. Farrell, later appointed him Chief of the Police of the Federal Capital. Due to the political events that occurred in the city on October 9, 1945, which culminated in General Perón's resignation from the positions he held, he presented his resignation to the Federal Headquarters, but 9 days later he returned to office. (Castelo Antonio Emilio. 1996-459).

Corrientes is one of the four provinces where Perón lost the presidential elections of 1946, the Senate of the Nation sanctions the law of Federal Intervention in Corrientes. In the section of September 4, 1947, the Senate of the Nation considers the dispatch of the constitutional business commission that advised the sanction of the Federal Intervention Law as approved in the

Chamber of Deputies. The Ministry of the Interior delivered to the Senate several files containing electoral and legal documentation and complaints from organizations and citizens against the Corrientes government. Senator Antille founded the need to sanction the law by expressing that it is necessary to intervene, not to overwhelm the government or the intervened territory, but to guarantee the exercise of the institutions. General Juan Filomeno Velazco was appointed Intervenor of the province, who took office on September 12, 1947. (Aguirre Orlando Raúl. 2001.34-35).

Regarding the intervention, Félix Luna says "*it is an unjustifiable abuse that adds one more stain to the history of the Perón government in relation to the stability of the institutions and respect for Federalism.*" (Luna Félix 1984-81).

In October 1948, Velazco resigned from office for having accepted the candidacy for governor for the elections that would institutionally normalize the province as a candidate of the Peronist party with the formula Juan Filomeno Velazco Governor and Fernando Irastorza for vice governor. He won the 1948 elections and took office on March 12, 1949, until June 4, 1952. In this regard, Germán Wiens adds "*...In 1948, political sectors allied with Intervenor Velazco offered him to run as a candidate for Governor. of the Province, calls for elections and resigns. The elections were held the same year and gave rise to the victory of the formula that he led accompanied by Fernando Irastorza as vice president. Thus, General Velazco becomes the first Peronist governor in the democratic history of the province, beginning a stage of true transformations throughout the Corrientes geography through public works, in Housing, Education, Health, Justice, Roads and Security...*". (Wiens German.2006).

During his administration, the Provincial Constitution was reformed with the purpose of adapting it to the National Constitution, which had been reformed in March 1949. On September 14, 1949, Law No. 1 was passed: 394 approving the province's public works and road plans. In the Capital, suburban neighborhoods were built for the most modest classes, the first housing plan for workers was executed, Costanera Avenue was expanded, the Port was urbanized and the accesses to the city were paved. The buildings of the Palace of Justice, the Ministry of Finance and the Bank of the Nation were built. In the city of Esquina he carried out the following works: the Municipal Palace, the Municipal

Slaughterhouse, the San Roque Hospital and the Post Office. The Investment Institute of the Province of Corrientes was created, as an autonomous entity, forming part of the Ministry of Finance, Public Works and Economy: with the objective of promoting forestry, agricultural and livestock development, establishment of industries, places of tourism, urban planning, constructions, thus the improvement of the different areas of the provinces. The Tipoi spinning factory is established by law No. 1501, exempting it from all provincial and municipal taxes. At the end of his term as governor in 1952 he served as National Senator of the province of Corrientes, until his death in the city of Córdoba on December 29, 1956. (Castelo Antonio Emilio. 1996-462).

In the different publications of the newspaper La Mañana we find announcements about the workers' demands regarding salaries and working conditions that they made to the industrial sector. They also refer to unemployment in rural areas, the majority of the province's laborers went to the Federal Capital and the Chaco, attracted by the good wages, this claim shows that the economic means that the workers have are insufficient to cover your basic needs. (Diario La Mañana 1949, March to July).

In the words of the press "*...Worker unrest is an undeniable reality, strikes occur in different areas of the country for the same cause: demands for improved salaries...*" (Diario La Mañana 1949, March 13 -3).

Other articles in the newspaper mention the Difficulties that are created in production: on the one hand, resolutions from the organizations in charge of controlling trade appear intended to govern these activities and what they generate are inconveniences, for this sector and the producers make their claims. to the state, and it responds with the following measure "*...the Bank will grant special loans with or without real guarantee, to producers who directly exploit the soil, whether they are farmers or ranchers. small producers who are dedicated to mixed exploitation (...) the granting of these loans, which must be subject to special regulations, will have the purpose of providing resources to producers for tilling the fields, harvesting crops, acquiring fertilizers and seeds ...*". We can mention among other laws issued by the government, Law No. 1484 "*...authorizes the creation in the city of Mercedes of a school-factory of professional orientation for the industrialization of stone...*" (Official Gazette of the Province of Corrientes 1950 - 2).

Copy of the newspaper La Mañana
September 29, 1949.

Findings.

The first findings that we obtained have to do with the temporal delimitation that coincided with the development and rise of the Justicialist government of Juan Domingo Perón, at that time Argentina was a party, the so-called Peronist party was supported by the growth of real wages, and the State spending tripled in that same period: workers' housing, sports fields, cider and Christmas toys, vacations on behalf of unions, schools, homes, hospitals and polyclinics, and the province of Corrientes was not left out of these benefits. During this administration, the opposition newspaper La Mañana, directed by Elías Abad, was not subject to censorship or closure; but as in the rest of the country, the opposition sectors did not have access to the means of oral communication.

Conclusion.

After the above, we can say that the Correntina Press, in this case the newspaper La Mañana, reflects the economic situation that the province is going through, which is not immune to the changes that are being experienced in the national order. Through these articles we can know and point out everything that was published in economic matters during this government administration of General Filomeno Velazco in 1949. The shortages of products and the increase in prices are exposed in these notices, the majority are food of first necessity, being the public, the consumer, on whom they impact when purchasing it, the conflicts that occur in production also have their place in these publications, along with worker unrest. His government management marked a stage in which public works multiplied in the Capital and in the Departments of the province of Corrientes.

The press in the provincial territory is a vehicle for the dissemination of ideas and its influence on society

is open to progress, as well as a forum for the permanent defense of freedom in Argentina.

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